

Table 2 (continued)

Line or variety	Pedigree or origin	Reaction ^a to	
		Stem rot	Bacterial blight
HAU 6-163-2	(Jaya/Palman 246)	9	9
UPRM 202	(Basmati Mutant)	9	5
UPRM 500	Hansraj Mutant	9	5
PAU 1-608-A	(Basmati 370/IR8-36)	7	5
PAU 41-30-6-2-5	(Phulpattas 72/Mutant 65)	9	9
PAU 128-1191-PR 303	(IR305-3-17-1-3/IR661-1-140-3)	1	5
CRR 89-5-1-1 RPSC 14	(Ratna/Domsiah)	3	5
CRR 89-5-4-1 RPSC-51	(Ratna/Domsiah)	3	5
CRR 89-5-4-2 RPSC-52	(Ratna/Domsiah)	9	7
CR 167-10	(Ratna/Early Prolific)	5	3
CR 206-6176-260	(Vijaya/Domsiah)	1	3
CR 209-6253-262	(Ratna/Domsiah)	5	3
FH 661		9	7
RP 967-4-1-2-4	(Improved Sabarmati/Sona)	9	3
ADT 32	(IR20/Pusa 33)	9	5
ADT 14166	(Pusa 140/Pusa 33)	3	9
ADT 14185	(Pusa 140/Ratna)	5	5
TRB 63	Basmati Mutant	9	5
SST ₁ - 1898	Punjab	9	7
SST ₁ - 1906	Punjab	3	7
SFC III	(IR8/NP 49)	9	1
R 575	Himachal Pradesh	1	7
O 12990-2/6-10-2	(IR8/Pankli 203)	1	7
IR4422-480-2	(IR2049-134-2/IR2061-125-31)	1	5
IR8073-231-3-3	(IR4-11/IR2035-290-2-3)/IR2153-26-3	3	5
IR9752-303-3-1-3	(IR28/Kwang-Chang-Ai)/IR36	9	3
Nong Nghiep 75-5	(IRS/D 268)	9	5

^aBased on the Standard Evaluation System for Rice Scales.

Pathogenic variability in *Xanthomonas oryzae*

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Thirty-six rice varieties were artificially infected in the field with 24 isolates of *Xanthomonas oryzae* (Uyeda et Ishiyama) Dowson in September 1973 and April 1974. The objective was to select suitable parents for determining genes for resistance and probable differentials for research on pathogenic specialization.

Twenty-six of the varieties were selected on the basis of their known reactions to 1 or 2 virulent isolates of *X. oryzae*; 16 were morphological markers of the 12 linkage groups in rice, included to identify characters associated with resistance.

The rices were artificially infected by the clipper method developed by Kauff-

man, using 2-day-old cultures suspended in sterile distilled water. The optical density was adjusted to 1.5 with Spectronic-20 at 620 nm. The spread of infection was measured (in centimeters) below the point of infection 15 days later.

The infection generally spread more in September than in April, with some notable exceptions. The response to seasonal factors in variety-isolate interactions was differential (see table).

Differential varieties should have short growth duration (120-130 days or less) and be insensitive to photoperiod. Short-duration varieties facilitate the multiplication and maintenance of pure seeds, the raising of seedlings to the flag-leaf stage for artificial infection, and other operations. Differential varieties should also show clear-cut resistant and susceptible reactions (the spread of infection in susceptible reaction should exceed 10 cm).

BJ1, Wase Aikoku 3, AC3550, and AC616 were completely resistant to 9 isolates, and, therefore, poor candidates as differentials, but good resistance

Differential reaction between isolate and rice varieties between September and April inoculations in Madras.

Variety	Isolates showing differential reaction
AC616	C
JBS376	C H201
AC806	C
AC5169	H J
Pirurutong	J H110 H146
Sigadis	H14 H1110 H66 H100
AC1063	D
ARC 142	H24
AC5607	H167 H200
T1242	H167 H100
MNP153	H167
SLO 16	H200
AC467	H200
Vijaya	H200 H201
JBS376	H34
M18	H201 H34
Early Prolific	H201
AC1224	H201
Lacrosse/Zenith-Nira	H110 H146 G
MNP153	H100
MNP152	G

donors. One or two of this group, however, could be included in the differential set to detect new virulent races in a region.

PTB 10, Cauvery, IR8, and TN1, being susceptible to all isolates, are also poor differential candidates. TN1 might be included as a test variety in infection studies.

The following appear to be good candidates as differentials: AC616, AC5169, AC3551, AC1063, ARC11249, ARC142, AC5607, JBS376, Bluebelle, and Lacrosse/Zenith Nira. Only Sigadis had consistently low infection against all isolates in kharif and is, therefore, a good donor for resistance to Indian isolates.

The variability of the pathogen and its response to environmental fluctuation suggest the need for a rigid standardization of infection procedures. ■

Relation between leaf blast and neck blast disease on paddy in trials during 1980 kharif in India

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This study sought to understand the relationship between leaf blast and neck

blast on various cultures of paddy in national screening nurseries (NSN-1 and 2) and the International Rice Blast Nursery (IRBN) trials conducted in 1980 at V. C. Farm, Mandya. Information from the entries screened — 290 in NSN-1, 285 in NSN-2, and 264 in IRBN — showed the variable reaction of cultures to blast and disease incidence.

The data for disease incidence (see figure) indicate that the lowest number of cultures reacted to neck blast in NSN-1, with a disease score range of 7-9. In the NSN-2 trial, the highest number of cultures reacted to leaf blast, with a score range of 4-6. In all three trials, a high number of entries reacted to neck blast (0-3 score range). The leaf blast score was 4-6. In all trials, 31-36% of the cultures had neck blast in the score range of 4-6.

The variability in disease reaction and

Rice cultures showing variable reactions to leaf and neck blast. Karnataka, India, 1980.

number of cultures reacting to the two stages of blast may be due to the variable agroclimatic factors prevailing during the season, variable inoculum poten-

tiality at the time of infection, and the resistant reaction of some cultures to the pathogen. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Rice varietal resistance to brown planthopper

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A total of 1,070 varieties (1,000 ARC, 20 IRRI, and 50 from other sources) were evaluated to identify better sources of brown planthopper (BPH) resistance as well as to study the mechanism of resistance in selected varieties. In a mass-screening replicated test, resistance (less than 1.5 score on a 0-5 scale) was shown by only 18 varieties: ARC5500, ARC5754, ARC5757, ARC5764, ARC5780, ARC5838, ARC5917, ARC5973, ARC5981, ARC5988, ARC1 2864, ARC1 3854, ARC1 3966, ARC14394, ARC13507, ARC14539, ARC14766 A, and ARC14703. Moderate resistance (1.6 to 3.0) was observed in 73 varieties. ARC5780, ARC5973, and ARC12864 exhibited less damage and were comparable to the resistant check PTB 33.

A high degree of nonpreference and

antibiosis mechanism was evident in ARC5780 and ARC5988. Varieties less preferred by BPH nymphs were also less suitable for adult oviposition, with the exception of ARC1 3854, ARC 14766 A, and ARC15507. On selected resistant varieties nymphal mortality was higher and nymphal development was longer by 3-7 days, than in the susceptible check TN1. Resistant varieties bore a higher number of probing marks made by insects during attempts to feed. Feeding on resistant varieties was 6.6 to 11.9 times less than on the susceptible check. Insects lost 9 to 40% of their body weight while feeding on resistant varieties, but gained 27% on a susceptible variety. Some varieties showing moderate damage reaction (ARC59 18, ARC10443, ARC13984, ARC14529, and ARC14864) also exhibited more feeding marks, greater amounts of honeydew excretion, and higher gain in body weight of the insects, confirming a moderate degree of resistance.

The susceptible reaction in mass-screening tests of resistant varieties (IR26, IR28, IR30, IR32, IR34, IR36, IR38, and IR40) to different biotypes

and of donors such as Mudgo and ASD7 has further confirmed the possibility of different biotypes in the Hyderabad, India, area. Statistical analysis of more than 1,000 varieties showed that lemma and palea color was not associated with BPH resistance. ■

Research on brown planthopper biotypes in China

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This study was part of the brown planthopper collaborative project sponsored by IRRI. To determine the brown planthopper (BPH) biotype that occurs in different regions of China, responses of different rice varieties to BPH, the survival rate of nymphs, population buildup, and honeydew excretion of the insect were measured.

Twelve rice varieties with resistance genes were tested (see table).

BPH types were collected from 35 counties and cities in China, including